

Presenting the Notion of an Energy Shaft

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A property of the Fine Structure Constant, serving as an implicit definition of its, is that

$$\alpha \hbar c = \frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \quad (1),$$

with α being the Fine Structure Constant, $\hbar$ the Reduced Planck's Action Constant, c the Vacuum Speed of Light, e the absolute value of the Electron Charge, and ϵ_0 the Vacuum Permittivity.

It is notionally noteworthy that the RHS of (1) is equal to the product of the opposite of the Coulomb Potential Energy U_n of the Bohr Model Hydrogen Electron and the respective allowed Bohr Radius r_n :

$$\frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0} = \left[- \left(- \frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r_n} \right) \right] \cdot r_n = (-U_n) \cdot r_n \quad (2).$$

On the other hand, as deducible from the Virial Theorem applied for a Central Conservative, Inverse-Square-Law, Attractive Force, the Kinetic Energy K_n of the above Bohr Electron following its n^{th} allowed Orbit is equal to the opposite of the half of the entailed, algebraically negative, Coulomb Potential Energy U_n ; equivalently, the adjoint Total Mechanical Energy E_n is equal to half the Potential one. Therefore,

$$\frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0} = 2K_n \cdot r_n = K_n \cdot (2r_n) = |E_n| \cdot (2r_n) \quad (3);$$

namely, given (1), the product of the Bohr Electron Kinetic Energy K_n (or, equivalently, the absolute value of the Bohr Electron Total Mechanical Energy E_n) and the respective Orbit Diameter $2r_n$ (representing a pertinent Energy Effectiveness Topological Extent) equals $\alpha \hbar c$.

Viewing the aforementioned product as interweaving the Bohr Electron Kinetic Energy quantum-mechanically available value and a conjugate Topological Measure of its we are inspired to ascribe to it the Notion of Bohr Electron Energy Shaft,

$$\Gamma_{Bohr} \equiv K_n \cdot (2r_n) \quad (4),$$

being Universal over all canonical instances of the Quantum Number n .